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Emotional intelligence for effective on academic performance of higher secondary students

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The main objective of the present study was to construct the emotional intelligence scale and to examine its relationship with academic performance among higher secondary students. The random sampling technique was used to select one hundred and nineteen students who were in the eleventh standard. The survey instrument was prepared wherein a large number of items based on the contemporary theoretical model of emotional intelligence were prepared. The academic performance was assessed on the basis of CGPA scores and performance satisfaction of students. The principal components factor analysis was performed which indicated evidence of five factors which were labeled as self-awareness, self-motivation, managing relation and empathy, mood management and self enhancement. The total scale explained 39% of variance wherein the individual components explained 16, 10, 6, 4 and 3 % of variance respectively. The correlation results indicated that of the five components of emotional intelligence self-awareness and self-motivation predicted academic performance while managing relationship and mood management failed to predict academic performance. Finally, self enhancement predicted previous academic scores and performance satisfaction relative to friends. Implications of the study are discussed.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, academic performance, self-awareness

The present system of education in India is putting the children in a race where performance is considered very important for future success. The students are required to play active role in the attainment of knowledge. The earlier educational system was more focused on rote learning and the learning process was teacher centered and unidirectional in nature. In recent years substantial changes in the teaching methodology and in the educational input delivery system is evident. The students are evaluated on a range of dimensions which includes academic performance, co-curricular activities and personality domains. The school administration is focusing on personality development of the student's to facilitate their successful academic achievement. The present education system is making all efforts to provide quality education to the students and developing the crucial emotional competencies among children such as emotional intelligence.

In recent years, low test scores and accountability standards have been the focus of education. However, the broader mission of education becomes clouded when effectiveness is defined solely or even primarily on the basis of performance on standardized assessment models. Test scores reflect the narrow emphasis of schooling rather than the broader mission of education. A healthy school climate focusing on academic, career, and leadership development requires an emphasis on affective or emotional learning as much as on academic or cognitive learning. Learning and applying emotional intelligence skills contribute to academic and career success is profusely reported by professions and educationalists. There is growing research that connects emotional intelligence and emotional skills to achievement, productivity, career success, personal health, resilience, job performance and leadership (Gardner, 1983, 1993, 1997; Goleman, 1995, 1997; Sternberg, 1985, 1990; Salovey & Mayer, 1997; Epstein, 1998; Weisenger, 1985, 1998; Townsend & Gephart, 1997; Nelson & Low, 2003., Shukla

& Nagar, 2013). Within this backdrop the present research was designed to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence with academic performance in the school context.

A number of scholars have noted that academic success depends on several type of intelligence and components of emotions. IQ alone is no more the measure for success; emotional intelligence, social intelligence, and even luck contribute to a person's success (Goleman, 1995). In the work place training is provided to employees and managers so that they become more aware of the components of emotional intelligence and may improve themselves. Thus, it seems that emotional intelligence is considered nowadays vital for success and that integration of EQ components in the course curriculum may probably enhance the student achievement and may contribute to their success. In the present study attempts is been made to construct a scale of emotional intelligence suitable for the higher secondary students and thereafter to examine its linkages with academic performance.

In some private school of United States students are given lessons on emotional intelligence across the curriculum which is considered as an exhaustive program in social and emotional education called "Success for Life." (Pasi, 1997). Evidence exist that emotional well-being is a predictor of success in academic achievement and job success among others. Finnegan (1998) argues that schools should help students learn the abilities underlying emotional intelligence. Possessing some of these abilities can lead to achievement from the formal education years of the child and adolescent to the adult's competency in being effective in the workplace. Parker and others (2005) examined the impact of emotional intelligence on the successful transition from high school to university. Results revealed that academically successful students had significantly higher levels of several different emotional and social competencies. These findings suggest that emotional intelligence plays an important role in the successful transition from high school to university.

A recent study conducted by Mestre and others (2006) on Spanish adolescents revealed that emotional intelligence correlated

positively with teacher ratings of academic achievement and adaptation. Similarly a recent study conducted by Yahaya and others (2011) investigated the relationship between the identified five dimensions of emotional intelligence, namely self awareness, emotional management, self motivation, empathy, interpersonal skills and academic performance. The result revealed that self-awareness, self motivation and empathy predicted academic performance. Consistent results were obtained in the Indian context Kattakar (2010) where a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement was found.

On the basis of many prior research findings it can be concluded that the components of emotional intelligence have some linkages with academic performance and achievement. The CBSE education system is designed to provide the students with a platform which encourages their participation in scholarly activities besides teaching so as to enhance their EQ levels. Within this backdrop the present study attempts to construct emotional intelligence scale for higher secondary students and thereafter to validate the emotional intelligence scale to predict the Academic performance.

Method

Subjects

One hundred and nineteen students from a co-ed English medium school who have passed high school from the CBSE board were randomly selected to participate in the present study. Survey questionnaire were distributed to 68 males and 51 females belonging to Science and Commerce stream of a senior secondary school. The students were comparable across major demographical variables like age and socio economic status.

Instruments

A brief survey instrument was prepared. In the first section of the survey the respondents were required to furnish their demographical information like age, sex, socio economic status and so forth. In the second section the items on emotional intelligence were prepared while the last section was devoted to record the student's objective performance and performance satisfaction. A brief description of the measures is given below:

Demographic information: Items in this section were related to understand the background information about the respondents. Some of the items were related to age, gender, parent's job, number of siblings, subjects selected in the standard eleventh and so forth.

Assessment of emotional intelligence: A questionnaire was designed to measure emotional intelligence of higher secondary level students. This questionnaire is designed to provoke reflection about areas of emotionality which student should have expand or develop. Based on the contemporary theoretical models of emotional intelligence a total of 71 items were prepared. Items were prepared on different components of emotional intelligence. For instance, some statements were related with motivation, awareness and concern for self and others. Furthermore, some items were focused on mood management strategy and interpersonal relationship.

Assessment of academic performance: To assess the objective and subjective performance the respondents were required to report the CGPA obtained in their tenth standard besides reporting their grades subject wise. There were few subjective questions which were

related with their level of satisfaction with their performance and performance satisfaction relative to their friends.

Procedures

A brief survey instrument was distributed in the classroom setting. The students from biology, mathematics and commerce stream were selected at random and were asked to assemble in their respective classes in small groups. The researcher read the instructions loudly and thereafter explained the details regarding the manner in which responses were to be recorded. The participants were assured that their responses will be completely confidential and anonymous and that no individual questionnaire would be shown to school authorities.

Results

Factor analysis results

The participant's responses on the seventy one items of the emotional intelligence questionnaire were subjected to a principal component factor analysis using Keiser's criterion of factor extraction. The rotated factor loading indicated evidence of five factors having an Eigen value more than one. In the order of extraction the factor were labeled as self awareness, self-motivation, managing relation and empathy, mood management, self enhancement. These five factors together accounted for 39% of variance wherein the individual factors contributed of 16, 10, 6, 4 and 3 % of variance respectively. A brief description of these component scales are given below:

Factor 1: Self-Awareness. The ratings of the items which loaded on the first factor were summed together to give this seven item subscale. These factors were characterized by a feeling of awareness of themselves as well as others. The items that defined this factor were related to recognize our own emotions as well as others through their facial expressions. It is also about knowing one's own strengths, limitations and self esteem. There are seven items which defines the students' competence and awareness of their strengths and weaknesses. Some of the items measure the degree to which the students are able to learn from experience and how to overcome the negative thoughts. The reliability coefficient (Cronbach α) computed on the seven items of the self-awareness scale was .66.

Factor 2: Self-motivation.

This subscale measures the extent to which student motivate them, don't give up easily, having firm determination to complete the task. People with this competency are results-oriented, with a high drive to meet their objectives and standards. They are ready to get fresh ideas from wide variety of resources, Set challenging goals, find ways to do things better. The high score in this six item scale represents a high degree of self-motivation. The internal consistency among the items (Cronbach's α) was found to be .50.

Factor 3: Managing Relations and empathy. This subscale consists of six items. It measures the extent to which the students are able to convince people, anticipate and satisfy their need. Other items are focused on assessing the cooperative nature of the participants. The items on empathy deal with one's ability to understand the feelings transmitted through verbal and nonverbal messages, to provide emotional support to people when needed, and to understand the links between others' emotions and behavior. Cronbach's α was .60 on this factor.

Table 1: Principal Component Factor analysis indicating loadings on the Emotional Intelligence items

Sr. Items	Factors				
	1	2	3	4	5
1. In challenging situations, I give up easily because I believe I will fail.	-.10	.44	.02	-.01	.27
2. I start any activity with the firm determination to complete it.	.21	.41	.01	.10	.44
3. I work hard to shape my bright future.	.10	.26	.10	.06	.60
4. I don't easily give up even I received setbacks.	-.04	.67	.13	.01	.13
5. By looking at their facial expressions I recognize the emotions people are experiencing.	.64	-.10	.14	.04	-.14
6. I am able to influence the opinion of elders.	.29	-.01	.25	-.14	.42
7. I am able to convince people.	.12	.04	.58	.01	.16
8. Obstacles and setbacks may delay me a little, but don't stop me.	.20	.54	.04	.07	.380
9. I seek out fresh ideas from wide variety of sources.	.11	.55	.08	.12	-.08
10. I am result oriented with a strong drive to meet my objectives.	-.03	.11	.16	.07	.50
11. I am always trying to learn how to improve my performance including asking advice from people younger than me.	.49	.24	.15	.17	.30
12. I am committed to my goals.	.11	.34	.20	.17	.44
13. I forgive myself for my mistakes and take it lightly.	-.05	.03	.02	.28	-.36
14. I am not much disappointed when someone criticizes me.	.02	.19	-.07	.47	.04
15. I have control over my emotions.	-.06	.16	.15	.52	-.07
16. When I have problems that create undue tension, I try to relax and gain a feeling of tranquility (calm and quite) so I can reevaluate things.	.19	.20	.20	.35	.08
17. I anticipate people's need and try to satisfy them.	.31	.18	.44	-.01	-.07
18. When another person tells me about an important event in his or her life, I almost feel as though I have experienced this by myself	.30	.11	.46	-.01	-.33
19. When I am in aggressive mood I know how to control that in few minutes.	-.12	-.01	.03	.67	.12
20. My impulses or distressing emotions don't often get the best of me at school.	-.17	-.01	.06	.01	.52
21. I adjust rapidly when situations changes.	.08	.38	.47	.21	.02
22. I take the lead whenever there is opportunity to do so.	.10	.25	.39	-.24	.23
23. I always bother about others what they are thinking about me.	.46	-.14	-.03	-.11	-.04
24. I present ideas in a way that engages others and inspires them to achieve more.	.42	.09	.19	.26	-.08
25. I can handle disagreement of others and confrontations positively.	.04	-.06	.33	.55	.19
26. I am able to identify when I am starting to feel under pressure.	.39	.18	.19	-.04	.04
27. I am able to express my emotions in a appropriate manner.	.22	-.20	.03	.42	.17
28. I am aware of situations that cause me to think negatively.	.42	.10	-.01	.03	.04
29. I do not become dependent when things go wrong.	-.10	.06	.41	.06	.17
30. I have positive outlook of life.	.23	.23	-.01	.26	.42
31. I take in to a account the input received from others when making a decisions.	.54	.21	-.20	.35	.09
32. I can able to maintain a calm appearance when my situations become uncomfortable.	.01	.02	.29	.55	-.05
33. If someone scolds me that moment I start crying and blaming myself.	.16	-.40	.15	-.28	.18

Factor 1: Self Awareness. 2: Self-Motivation. 3: Managing Relations and Empathy 4: Mood Management. 5: Self-Enhancement.

Factor 4: Mood Management. The items on this factor reflected control of emotions and feelings. Some of the items are related to measure the levels of disappointment even in situation when someone criticizes them. Other items measure the emotional balance, confronting the people in a positive way and know how to express their emotion in appropriate manner. This component reflects how to be calm even when situations become uncomfortable.

The reliability coefficient computed on these seven items of the mood management scale was .69.

Factor 5: Self-Enhancement- This subscale is comprised of seven items. Some of the items reflecting high loading were related to working hard for a better future, result orientation with a drive to meet the objectives, goal clarity and positive outlook in life .Cronbach's α was .48

Table 2: Correlation analysis depicting relationship between components of emotional intelligence with Academic Performance

Academic Performance	CGPA Scores at standard Tenth		CGPA scores at standard Eleventh	
	Past Academic Scores	Present Academic Scores	Self satisfaction with own Performance	Performance satisfaction relative to friends
Components of Emotional Intelligence				
Self Awareness	.30**	.25**	.15*	.21**
Self Motivation	.35**	.19**	.20**	.17**
Managing Relations and Empathy	.13	.10	.05	.12
Mood Management	.15	.09	.11	.07
Self Enhancement	.22**	.12	.14	.15*

Correlation analysis

In order to predict the relationship of emotional intelligence with academic performance a correlation analysis was performed. The result of correlation analysis presented in table 2 revealed that of all the five components of emotional intelligence self awareness and self motivation were found to be the best predictor of all components of academic performance. In contrast, managing relations and empathy and mood management failed to predict academic performance. The result further revealed that self enhancement component of emotional intelligence predicted the past academic performance and satisfaction with performance relative to friends. In other words students exhibiting high self awareness and self motivation reported better academic performance.

Discussion and conclusion

One major objective of the present study was to develop emotional intelligence scale. The factor analysis results indicate evidence of five underlying dimensions labeled as: self-awareness, self-motivation, managing relations and empathy, mood management, self enhancement. The component scales appear to represent the major conceptual dimensions of emotional intelligence and indicate some theoretically interesting consistency (Bar-On, 1997, Mayer, Salovey, & Caruso, 2000; Golman, 1995). Parker et al (2004) concluded that major elements of emotional intelligence predicted academic success of students. In a similar vein the study conducted by Rode et al. (2004) revealed that emotional intelligence was related to academic performance because academic work is self directed, requiring high levels of self management. Therefore, individuals with high emotional intelligence would perform better academically. The major result of this study revealed that self-awareness is the most important factor of emotional intelligence scale which predicts both objective grades and satisfaction with one's performance relative to others. This self awareness is the key to sensitize a person of strength and weakness. Holahan and Sears (1995) found that those who acquire self confidence in their earlier years of study were more success full in their careers. In a recent study Johnson (2009) has noted that student possessing higher levels of self awareness with high intrinsic motivation will exhibit high academic performance. The result of this study possesses similarities from some other studies to a large extent (two factor study process questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) Emotional intelligence scale (Schutte et al., 1998) Research has proposed that academic performance seem to be linked with emotional intelligence. It seems that students who are particularly focused on motivating themselves and who are aware about their strength and weaknesses are likely to do well on objective indicators of performance and will exhibit higher levels of academic achievement (Raineri, 2010). It is certainly plausible that students who report a desire for hard work and aim to please their teacher with their hard work perform better in regular classroom assessments. The result has evidently showed that emotional intelligence could significantly predict academic achievement of college students. Consistent results were obtained by Abisamra (2000) where a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance was obtained on measures related to Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA which is considered as a single measure of overall performance (Garger, & Thomas, 1998). It seems that a student who is adept in emotional management could use such skills to ward off stress and anxiety associated with test taking and

examination. Furthermore ability to display interpersonal and intrapersonal skills may assist students to seek academic help from teachers, peers and resource person's intelligence. Based on the results it can be concluded that student's academic performance should be enhanced with the use of emotional intelligence training (Hammed, 2010). In order to obtain good academic performance and ensure future success in life apart from effective learning techniques components of emotional intelligence should also be developed through training by academic institutions.

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